

Gamma radiation effect on structure and photoluminescence properties of RE³⁺ (Tb³⁺/Ce³⁺) activated GdPO₄ phosphor

Sudheer Gurugubelli^a, Vemareddy Bheeram^a, Anima S. Dadhich^a, Abhijit Saha^b and Saratchandra Babu Mukkamala^{*a}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, GITAM Institute of Science, GITAM University, Visakhapatnam-530 045, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : mscbabu@yahoo.com

^bUGC-DAE consortium for Scientific Research, Kolkata-700 098, India

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Abstract : RE³⁺ (Tb³⁺/Ce³⁺) activated GdPO₄ phosphor has been synthesized by hydrothermal route at 150 °C using citric acid as chelating agent. The synthesized phosphor has been characterized by TEM, TG/DTA, Powder X-ray diffraction and photoluminescence spectra. GdPO₄ displayed green emission after doping with Tb³⁺. The influence of γ -radiation on structural and photoluminescence properties of GdPO₄ : Tb³⁺, Ce³⁺ was also examined at 5 and 300 kGy. Quenching of PL intensity was observed in GdPO₄ : Tb³⁺, Ce³⁺ after exposure to γ -radiation. Moreover, this phosphors exhibited high structural stability upon γ -radiation exposure.

Keywords : Gadolinium phosphate, hydrothermal synthesis, photoluminescence, γ -radiation.

Introduction

Rare-earth (RE) doped gadolinium based phosphors have been extensively investigated in recent years due to their unique optical applications such as tunable light-emitting diodes, lasers^{1,2}, mercury-free fluorescent lamps³, plasma display panels (PDPs)⁴, solid state lighting, field emission display devices, radiation dosimetry and γ -ray photography^{5,6}. Phosphate based phosphors are widely used when compared to other phosphor materials due to its high chemical stability and ecofriendly characteristics^{7,8}. Gadolinium phosphate (GdPO₄) is well known as multifunctional material with structural diversity among all other rare earth phosphates⁹. Its photoluminescent properties can be tuned by incorporating the rare earth elements into the host¹⁰. GdPO₄ emits intense green light luminescence after doping Tb³⁺ ions as a sequence of transitions ⁵D₄/⁷F_j (j = 3, 4, 5 and 6)¹¹. The photoluminescence brightness of Tb³⁺ doped GdPO₄ is significantly enhanced by incorporating the co-dopant, cerium (Ce³⁺) in its host lattice. High energy radiations such as X-rays and γ -rays may influence the displacement of at-

oms from their positions in the crystal lattice depending on the energy of ionization radiation^{12,13}. Ionizing radiation due to non-linear interaction of electronic excitations can play an important role in luminescence property of materials^{14,15}.

Furthermore, GdPO₄ act as promising MRI contrast agent through enhanced T1 relaxation due to more number of unpaired electrons in its atoms¹⁶. By incorporating the rare earth elements into Gd³⁺ host lattice, the luminescent property and drug carrier capacity of GdPO₄ are also enhanced¹⁷. It is well known that, citric acid is used as additive/chelating agent to synthesize the bio-ligand coated and surface modified phosphate based phosphors for biomedical applications¹⁸⁻²¹.

This study demonstrate the synthesis, characterization and properties of citric acid coated GdPO₄ : Tb³⁺ and GdPO₄ : Dy³⁺ phosphors. The luminescence emissions of GdPO₄ : Tb³⁺, Ce³⁺ has been examined under ultraviolet excitation. The structural stability of both compounds were tested after exposure to gamma radiation.

Results and discussion

Morphology and structure :

The morphology and structure of $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ was examined by transmission electron microscope (TEM) and selected area diffraction (SAED). As shown in Fig. 1, $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ exhibited needle like morphology with length and width of around 700 and 40 nm, respectively. No prominent morphological changes were observed in $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ phosphor after doping the rare earths into GdPO_4 . Fig. 1c depicts the SAED pattern taken from individual nano rod of $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ phosphor and also confirms that the interplanar distances (d-spacing) of as prepared $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ matched with PXRD analysis (Fig. 2). Analysis of $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) (Fig. 1d) confirmed the presence of Gd, P, Tb and O. The atom percentage ratio of Gd/P/O obtained from the EDX spectrum was almost similar to the standard atom ratio (1 : 1 : 4).

The crystallinity and phase purity of the products were examined by powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD)

analysis. Fig. 2 shows the PXRD patterns of undoped and Tb^{3+} doped GdPO_4 . The PXRD patterns of GdPO_4 and $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ are in good agreement with the values from JCPDS No. 39-0232 (Fig. 2), which reveals that all the products exhibit hexagonal phase GdPO_4 . Furthermore, except for a slight change in the intensity no additional peaks for other phases associated with the doped component were observed. This little variation in XRD peaks is due to difference in ionic radius of doped metal ions (1.80 Å for Gd^{3+} and 1.75 Å for Tb^{3+} ion).

Influence of γ -radiation on $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ was examined at 5 and 300 kGy doses. Except for a little change in intensity of peaks no change in peak position was observed after γ -irradiation at 5 kGy and 300 kGy. It is observed that γ -radiation did not influence the crystal structure of $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$.

Fig. 3 shows the results obtained from simultaneous TG-DTA on GdPO_4 . The TG curve indicates that the first weight loss of 4.4% in the temperature

Fig. 1. (a and b) TEM images of $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$, (c) SAED pattern and (d) EDX analysis.

Fig. 2. Powder XRD patterns of (a) GdPO_4 and (b) $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$.

Fig. 3. TG-DTA profile of GdPO_4 .

range 25–125 °C corresponding to the removal of physically absorbed water. The second step of mass loss of 21.8% in the temperature range 250–450 °C and a strong exothermic peak at about 350 °C in DTA supports the removal of organic moiety with crystallization of GdPO_4 . An endothermic peak in DTA found at 800 °C corresponds to the phase transformation.

The FT-IR spectra of GdPO_4 and $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ are shown in Fig. 4. The peaks at 1628 and 3454 cm^{-1} is due to bending and stretching vibrations of water molecules. The peak at 1079 cm^{-1} is a characteristic of the asymmetric stretching vibration of the P–O bond and the bands centered at 623 and 540 cm^{-1} are attributed to the bending vibration of O–P–O bond of PO_4^{3-} groups. Furthermore, the asymmetric stretching vibration mode of COO^- is appears at 1628 cm^{-1} and the band associated to the symmetric stretching vibrational mode of COO^- is appears at 1385 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of citric acid on the surface of phosphors.

Fig. 4. FT-IR spectra of (a) GdPO_4 and (b) $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$.

Photoluminescence properties :

Fig. 5 shows the photoluminescence spectra of $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$, $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}, \text{Ce} (1\%)$, $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}, \text{Ce} (5\%)$ [$\text{Gd}/\text{Tb}/\text{Ce} = 89 : 10 : 1$ (or) $85 : 10 : 5$]. The gadolinium ions (Gd^{3+}) consists of seven unpaired electrons in the 4f shell (unfilled), which is shielded by the completely filled 5s and 5p shells²². $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ phosphors consist of f-f transitions within 4f⁸ electron configuration of Tb^{3+} ion⁵. After photo excitation at 230 nm, Tb^{3+} ions exhibits four emission peaks at 484 nm ($^5\text{D}_4 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_6$) in the blue region, 550 nm ($^5\text{D}_4 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_5$) in the green region, 583 as well as 617 nm ($^5\text{D}_4 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_4$ and $^5\text{D}_4 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_3$) in the red region. The strong emission peak located at 550 nm corresponds to the magnetic-dipole-allowed transition of intense green emission. In addition, incorporation of cerium (Ce^{3+}) ion into $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ does not effect the emission peak position, but progressively enhances the photoluminescence intensity of $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$. The effect of γ -irradiation on optical properties of $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$, $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}, \text{Ce} (1\%)$, $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}, \text{Ce} (5\%)$ were also investigated at doses of 5 and 300 kGy and is shown in Fig. 5(b-d). Considerable decrease in the emission intensity was identified with increasing dose from pre-irradiated to 300 kGy. The decrease in luminescence intensity could be attributed to non-radiative transitions¹⁴. Fig. 6 shows the colour space chromaticity diagram of $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ (10.0 mol %), $\text{Ce} (5.0 \text{ mol } \%)$ phosphor. After doping 10.0 mol % of Tb^{3+} into GdPO_4 , the emission of green colour was analyzed with the help of the CIE chromaticity coordinates.

Fig. 5. Photoluminescence spectra of (a) before irradiation $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}, \text{Ce}^{3+}$, (b) γ -irradiated $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$, (c) γ -irradiated $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}, \text{Ce}^{3+}$ (1%) and (d) γ -irradiated $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}, \text{Ce}^{3+}$ (5%).

Fig. 6. The CIE chromaticity diagram of $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}, \text{Ce}^{3+}$ phosphor under 230 nm photo excitation.

Experimental

Materials :

All chemicals were of analytical grade and used without any further purification. $\text{Tb}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Dy}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich,

USA, $\text{Gd}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ from Acros Organics, Belgium, disodium hydrogen phosphate and lauric acid from Merck-India.

Preparation of $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}, \text{Ce}^{3+}$:

Double distilled water was used throughout the synthesis. The standard stock solutions of 0.2 M $\text{Gd}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Tb}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were prepared. 1.0 mmol of $\text{Gd}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (5.0 mL, 0.2 M) and 2.0 mmol of citric acid (10 mL, 0.2 M) were taken in 50 ml beaker and stirred continuously for 25 min to get the turbid solution of gadolinium citrate complex. Later, an aqueous solution containing 1.0 mmol of disodium hydrogen orthophosphate (5.0 mL, 0.2 M) was added. Then, the solution was transferred into Teflon lined stainless steel autoclave, and heated hydrothermally at 150 °C for 20 h. After cooling down to room temperature, the precipitate obtained was separated by centrifugation and washed with deionized water. Then, it was finally dried overnight under air at 60 °C. For synthesis of RE^{3+} doped LaPO_4 , a fraction of $\text{Gd}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was re-

placed with $\text{Tb}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (10%) and $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 or 5%).

Characterization :

The thermogravimetry measurements were carried out on “Mettler Toledo TGA/DSC-1” apparatus under nitrogen atmosphere. Photoluminescence of the solid sample was recorded using “Perkin-Elmer LS-55 Luminescence Spectrometer” at room temperature. Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) pattern was recorded on “PANALYTICAL X’Pert pro Powder X-ray diffractometer” with graphite monochromatic Cu K_α ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) radiation. TEM images were recorded using Philips CM-200 transmission electron microscope (TEM). EDX analysis was performed using field emission scanning electron microscopy (Hitachi S-4800, Japan). Then, all these obtained GdPO_4 phosphors were divided into small portions and packed in a plastic vials with para film. These samples were exposed to gamma radiation by using ^{60}Co gamma cell (^{60}Co – source capacity 3700 Ci) at a dose rate 2.95 kGy/h at room temperature. All the samples were irradiated at doses of 5 and 300 kGy by γ -radiation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, RE^{3+} (Tb^{3+} and Ce^{3+}) doped GdPO_4 was synthesized through hydrothermal route using citric acid as chelating agent. $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ exhibited needle like morphology with length and width $\sim 700\text{--}800$ and $\sim 40\text{--}50$ nm, respectively. $\text{GdPO}_4 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ emitted green emission at 550 nm corresponding to $^5\text{D}_4 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_5$ transition. Progressive decrease in the photoluminescence intensity was identified on increasing γ -irradiation progressively from 5 kGy to 300 kGy probably due to loss of heat energy through non-radiative process.

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References

1. L. Zhang, H. Jiu, Y. Fu, Y. Sun, P. Chen, Y. Li and S. Ma, *Mater. Lett.*, 2013, **101**, 47.

2. R. Kumar, T. Email, D. P. Bisen and N. Brahme, *Res. Chem. Intermed.*, 2014, **40**, 1771.
3. A. Mbarek, G. Chadeyron, D. Boyer, D. Avignan, M. Fourati, D. Zambon and R. Mahiou, *J. Luminesc.*, 2014, **145**, 335.
4. K. Y. Jung, D. Y. Lee and Y. C. Kang, *J. Luminesc.*, 2005, **115**, 91.
5. H. Song, L. Zhou, L. Li, F. Hong and X. Luo, *Mater. Res. Bull.*, 2013, **48**, 5013.
6. J. Kaewkhao, N. Wantana, S. Kaewjaeng, S. Kothan and H. J. Kim, *J. Rare Earths*, 2016, **34**, 583.
7. Y. Li, M. A. Hongping, H. Youjie, Y. Qinghua, L. Chenxia, D. Degang and X. Shiqing, *J. Rare Earths*, 2016, **34**, 7.
8. A. Phuruangrat, N. Ekthammathat, S. Thongtem and T. Thongtem, *Res. Chem. Intermed.*, 2013, **39**, 1363.
9. K. N. Shinde, R. Singh and S. J. Dhoble, *J. Luminesc.*, 2014, **145**, 930.
10. I. P. Sahu, D. P. Bisen and R. Sharma, *Res. Chem. Intermed.*, 2016, **42**, 2791.
11. K. Park, M. H. Heo and S. J. Dhoble, *Mater. Chem. Phys.*, 2013, **140**, 108.
12. V. N. Rai, B. N. Raja Sekhar, S. Kher and S. K. Deb, *J. Luminesc.*, 2010, **130**, 582.
13. S. Gurugubelli, A. S. Dadhich, A. Saha and S. B. Mukkamala, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2016, **93**, 465.
14. A. K. Bedyal, Vinay Kumar, O. M. Ntwaeaborwa and H. C. Swart, *Radiat. Phys. Chem.*, 2016, **122**, 48.
15. C. B. Palan, K. A. Koparkar, N. S. Bajaj, A. Soni and S. K. Omanwar, *Res. Chem. Intermed.*, 2016, **42**, 7637.
16. H. B. Na, I. C. Song and T. Hyeon, *Adv. Mater.*, 2009, **21**, 2133.
17. Y. Tang, R. Mei, S. Yang, H. Tang, W. Yin, Y. Xu and Y. Gao, *Superlattices and Microstructures*, 2016, **92**, 256.
18. W. Di, J. Li, N. Shirahata, Y. Sakka, M. G. Willinger and N. Pinna, *Nanoscale*, 2011, **3**, 1263.
19. W. Di, M. G. Willinger, Rute, A. S. Ferreira, X. Ren, S. Lu and N. Pinna, *J. Phys. Chem. (C)*, 2008, **112**, 18815.
20. I. M. Nagpure, S. S. Pitale, E. Coetsee, O. M. Ntwaeaborwa, J. J. Terblans and H. C. Swart, *Opt. Mater.*, 2012, **34**, 1398.
21. N. O. Nunez, S. R. Liviano and M. Ocana, *J. Colloid and Interface Sci.*, 2010, **349**, 484.
22. P. Gupta, A. K. Bedyal, V. Kumar, Y. Khajuria, S. P. Lochab, S. S. Pitale, O. M. Ntwaeaborwa and H. C. Swart, *Mater. Res. Bull.*, 2014, **60**, 401.

